

Gypsum (50% of the gypsum requirement of the soil) plus 11.2 kg Zn/ha produced maximum grain yield. FYM alone or in combination with Zn was inferior even to 25% gypsum alone. □

Varietal differences in P uptake of rice on sodic soils

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We screened salt-tolerant varieties IR54, IR4563-52-1-1-3-6, IR9975-5-1, IR146-32-22-3, IR19661-131-1-2, M242, and Pokkali for P uptake in sodic soils. Cultivars were transplanted in 4 replications in field plots with pH 8.5-8.9, 9.0-9.4, and 9.5-10.0. N, P, and K were applied at 120, 26, and 25 kg/ha as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash. After harvest, grain and straw samples were analyzed for P content (Tables 1 and 2). Pokkali yielded best, followed by IR4563-52-

Table 1. Effect of soil alkalinity on grain yield and straw-to-grain ratio of paddy, Kanpur, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)				Straw:grain			
	pH 8.7	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	Average	pH 8.7	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	Average
IR54	2.5	1.8	0.5	1.6	1.8	2.4	6.4	3.5
IR4563-52-1-1-3-6	4.2	3.7	2.5	3.5	1.2	1.1	1.6	1.3
IR9975-5-1	4.2	2.4	1.7	2.8	1.3	1.7	2.8	1.9
IR14632-22-3	2.6	2.0	2.1	2.3	3.3	3.7	3.8	3.6
IR19661-131-1-2	3.1	2.8	2.2	2.7	2.0	1.9	1.7	1.8
M242	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.2	1.7	1.9	1.9
Pokkali	4.7	3.6	2.9	3.7	1.8	1.9	1.7	1.8
Average	3.4	2.7	2.1		1.9	2.1	2.8	

Table 2. Effect of soil alkalinity on total P uptake and percentage translocation in grain, Kanpur, India.

Variety	Total P uptake (kg/ha)				% translocation of P in grain			
	pH 8.7	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	Average	pH 8.7	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	Average
IR54	13.2	12.9	8.1	11.4	62.9	40.2	21.8	41.6
IR4563-52-1-1-3-6	22.1	17.9	11.7	17.2	72.3	72.5	58.0	67.6
IR9975-5-1	24.2	14.3	13.3	17.3	67.0	57.1	44.8	56.3
IR14632-22-3	20.1	21.4	18.6	20.3	41.4	32.6	36.9	33.5
IR19661-131-1-2	19.6	16.6	11.7	15.9	56.2	56.3	60.3	51.6
M242	14.4	12.5	13.1	13.3	56.3	55.2	55.3	55.6
Pokkali	26.2	19.0	14.3	19.8	65.3	63.7	65.4	64.8
Average	19.9	16.3	12.9		60.2	53.9	48.6	

1-1-3-6. IR54 yielded least. As pH increased, grain yield and P uptake decreased. Highest yielding varieties had

comparatively higher translocation of P in grains (Table 2). □

Pest management and control DISEASES

A possible source of resistance to rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)

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The occurrence of a new GSV strain (GSV 2) that can overcome the resistance gene to ordinary GSV 1 prompted us to search for new sources of resistance.

A perennial rice plant, Guang-Keng A/*Oryza rufipogon*/*Oryza longistaminata* (IRRI acc. no. 104315), was introduced from China in 1980. Plants were propagated by dividing tillers, and seedlings obtained in a natural set of these plants were tested for GSV 1 and GSV 2 infection (see table). Twenty to 130 viruliferous brown planthoppers (BPH) were allowed inoculation access for 2 to 4 d on the tillers and seedlings. Virus

Reaction of divided tillers and seedlings of Guang-Keng A/*Oryza rufipogon*/*Oryza longistaminata* (acc. no. 104315) to GSV 1 and GSV 2, IRRI, 1984.^a

Plant part tested	Plant type	Inoculated strain	Insects ^b (no./plants)	Plants (no.)		Virus recovery ^c			
				Inoculated	Infected	Plants (no.)		BPH (no.)	
						Tested ^d	Recovered	Tested	Infective
Tiller		GSV 1	20	18	0	—	—	—	—
		GSV 1	50	4	0	—	—	—	—
		GSV 1	130	4	1	1	0	20	0
		GSV 2	50	21	1	1	0	40	0
Seedling	Dwarf	GSV 1	20	1	1	1	1	16	1
		GSV 1	120	2	2	2	1	80	1
	Tall	GSV 1	20	3	1	1	0	17	0
		GSV 1	120	1	0	—	—	—	—
	Dwarf	GSV 2	25	9	9	—	—	—	—
		GSV 2	120	1	1	1	1	40	1
		GSV 2	20	4	3	2	1	123	1
		GSV 2	25	5	1	—	—	—	—
	Tall	GSV 2	120	2	0	—	—	—	—

^aInoculation was done 2 or 4 wk after sowing. ^b2 to 4 d inoculation access period. ^cDone at various times (15–210 d) after inoculation. ^dOnly infected plants were tested.

recovery tests were conducted on inoculated plants using virus-free BPH and the latex test confirmed the presence or

absence of the virus.

None of the 22 tillers inoculated with GSV 1 at 20 or 50 insects/tiller was